

Harmony of the Spheres: A Physics-Based Android Synthesizer and Controller with Gestural Objects and Physical Transformations

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces the concepts and principles behind *Harmony of the Spheres*, an Android app that investigates the sonic potential of objects in n -dimensional physical spaces with transforming properties. Using gestural multi-touch and accelerometer control, users can create musical objects in these spaces and interact with them, while they move and react to the physical conditions of the spaces. The properties of these objects can be arbitrarily mapped to sound parameters, either of an internal synthesizer or external systems, and they can be visualized in flexible ways. On a larger scale, users can make soundscapes by defining sequences of physical space conditions, each of which has an effect on the motion and properties of the physical objects.

1. INTRODUCTION

Spatial representations have gained increasing importance in interaction schemes with applications, especially since the rise of smart phones and tablets. In comparison with personal computers, these devices allow users to interact more directly and more physically with the objects represented on the screen, by touching and manipulating them with multiple fingers, moving and shaking the device, or pointing it in a direction and walking around. [1] An increasing number of musical and audio apps thus replace the traditional skeuomorphic systems containing knobs and sliders with more adventurous spatial representations. Most of these spaces directly contain what can be called musical objects, each of them producing sounds when they move around or when they interact with other objects. A few of these apps are based on physical models determining the objects' movements and interactions, which is probably directly inspired by mobile games using physical engines. However, in most of these physics apps the space itself does not seem to have any musical significance and sound seems to be almost uniquely generated when objects collide, which is of course directly analogous to the way

we experience physical reality.¹

With the app presented in this paper, *Harmony of the Spheres (HotS)*,² I investigate the potential of other kinds of mappings between the properties of objects in a simulated physical space and conceptual musical dimensions. I also investigate ways in which users can create and interact with objects and physical conditions of the space, using the user interface possibilities of current mobile devices. The concepts underlying the app are inspired by recent developments in mathematical music theory, specifically transformational theory. As the core of the app I developed a generalized physics model for n -dimensional spaces. The dimensions of such a space can be mapped, via custom mapping functions, to any musical dimensions, either of the internal synthesizer or of external systems, via OSC. Similarly, they can be mapped to any of the supported visual dimensions, such as spatial position or color. The space is populated with musical objects, called *spheres* (see Figure 1), which can have two kinds of motion. Their *inherent motion* is a multidimensional oscillating motion that is repeated infinitely, independently of physical conditions. Their *physical motion* is the motion caused by the current physical conditions of the space, which can change over time.

Users can interact with the app and create soundscapes by drawing spheres and their inherent motion in any of the n dimensions³ directly onto the screen. Simultaneously, they can define sequences of temporary *physical conditions*, including various types of gravity, spring collisions, friction, and viscosity, each of which lasts for a specified time before it is superseded by the next conditions. In the following sections, after a brief overview of conceptually related work, I will discuss the app's fundamental concepts on a technical level and describe the way the graphical user interface works.

¹ In his study of all musical iOS apps existing in early 2014, Kell and Wanderley [2] identify 23 applications of a type they call *ball sims*, which all generate sound upon collisions. Examples are Balls, Boinkss, Caestis, Catalyst, Gravitone, Gravity Beats, or Metalin. However, some apps in other categories are based on the same model, e.g. Bucephalus, Anchorage Spring, and Digital Collisions in the category *synth*, or Amos in *midiosc*. The category *novel* possibly includes several other ones, e.g. Soundrop. Conditions are the same on the other stores, where we find apps for other platforms such as Bounce 2, or Musyc (Android).

² The name is inspired by the ancient Pythagorean notion of the celestial objects creating an inaudible form of music, based on the harmonic ratios of their movements. The harmony of the spheres, also called *musica mundana* or *musica universalis*, formed one of the three kinds of music, along with *musica humana* and *musica instrumentalis*.

³ The dimensionality of the space can be varied at runtime, and visible dimensions can be switched by changing the visual mapping, in order to draw in all dimensions.

Figure 1. The main screen of *Harmony of the Spheres* with some spheres represented in five visual dimensions.

2. BACKGROUND

Recent developments in mathematical music theory emphasize the importance of musical spaces for the understanding of music. Transformational theory, for instance, models music as recursive sets of objects in logically structured spaces defined by group theory [3] or topos theory [4] and describes how different sets of objects relate to each other by finding intuitive transformations between them. The spacial representation that many musicians are still most familiar with, the score, is not sufficient to express the abstract relationships between the musical entities themselves. This is in line with recent findings in the theory of semantics, based on cognitive science. Gärdenfors, for instance, argues that conceptual spaces are fundamental learning, reasoning, and understanding and that our minds organize information in geometric and topological ways [5].⁴

Since the early developments of computer music, applications using spatial representations have played an important role. The UPIC system [6], for instance, mapped its two main visual dimensions to the musical parameters of pitch and time, in analogy to the score. Many other apps have since built on such spatial musical representations, allowing for more freedom in mapping visual to auditive parameters and allowing various synthesis techniques, e.g. IanniX [7] or Borderlands [8]. In an earlier research project I dealt with visual and interactive representations of mu-

sical spaces and transformations where visual dimensions could be arbitrarily mapped to the dimensions of the musical objects at runtime [9, 10].

On the other hand, several projects investigated the musical potential of mapping physical models to music beyond mere collision triggering as in most mobile apps to date, as noted in the introduction. Inspired by earlier instances of sonification of scientific models, such as in Xenakis' stochastic systems [11], or by the elaboration of perceptual theories such as Gabors acoustic quanta leading to granular synthesis [12], Sturm investigated the potential of a sonification of particle systems [13]. He placed the listener in a physical space surrounded by particles, mapped particle energy to frequency, proximity to the listener to amplitude, and spatial position directly to stereo or quad spatialization position. Others have since created more interactive applications based on mappings of physical models to music, such as RedUniverse⁵ or Perkins' recent work [14]. All these examples are based on either two- or three-dimensional spaces, but some of them allow for dynamic mappings between object properties such as position, velocity, or direction to sonic dimensions. Perkins' system, for instance, lets users draw an arbitrary mapping function for each mapped dimension.

⁴ In later chapters of his new book, Gärdenfors stresses the importance of action and force in relation to conceptual spaces, which is directly related to the ideas behind this project.

⁵ <http://www.fredrikolofsson.com/f0blog/?q=node/149>

3. THE UNIVERSE AND ITS VISUAL AND AUDITIVE MAPPINGS

In this early version of *Harmony of the Spheres* the spheres exist in a space or universe U , which can be one of three simple types of n -dimensional spaces. These options include \mathbb{R}^n and \mathbb{R}_m^n , which are simply the n -tuples of real numbers and the n -tuples of real numbers modulo m , respectively, as well as the bounded n -dimensional unit interval $[0, 1]^n$. At runtime, the users can redefine the number of dimensions if needed, without the possible consequence of losing information when shrinking the space.⁶

The space in itself has an abstract existence, independent of any musical or visual properties. The users can give meaning to any of the space's dimensions by mapping it to any number of audio parameters and visual parameters using a simple dialog shown at runtime. The *audio mappings* can either reach parameters of the internal synthesizer (written in C++ and included via the Android NDK), including frequency, amplitude, phase, panning, timbre, etc, all referring to oscillators or wavetable generators, or they can be used to control parameters of external sound generators, e.g. in a Max/MSP patch, via OSC. *Visual mappings* can again map any dimension of the space to any number of the available visual parameters, currently including x- and y-positions, size, color, and opacity. These mappings determine the way all spheres in U become visible and audible, each of them represented by an independent visual and an audible object. For instance, when mapped to the internal synthesizer, each sphere corresponds to one oscillator with its parameters being set to the values corresponding to the mapped space positions.

Formally, the audio mappings form a functional graph $AC \in N \times A$ where $N = 1, \dots, n$ is the set of dimension indices of U and A the set of audio parameters or external control parameters. The users can currently control these mappings using a set of drop down menus, one for each audio parameter, where the index of the dimension can be selected. Any such changes in mapping can be chosen to happen smoothly, using internal ramps, which is realized using interpolations between the value of the previously mapped dimensions and the newly mapped ones, a smooth parameter exchange so to speak. However, they can also be switched abruptly, if desired.

In a similar way, the visual mappings match the visual parameters V (currently including x- and y-positions, size, color, and opacity) with the elements of N , again as a functional graph $VC \in N \times V$. A simpler version of this matching principle, which directly linked visual and audio parameters, was first implemented in [9, 15]. Again, the users can control this using drop down menus, as with the audio mappings. Figure 2 shows how the mapping screen looks like in *HotS* for a five-dimensional space.

Figure 2. The mapping dialog of *HotS* showing the current visual and audio configuration.

4. THE SPHERES AND THEIR INHERENT MOTION

The focus of *HotS* are the musical objects that populate the spaces just described, the *spheres*. Apart from being moved by the physical conditions of the space, described in the next section, the spheres can have their inherent oscillatory motion as mentioned earlier. In mathematical and computational music theory, musical objects are often defined as simple points or vectors in musical spaces, with either absolute or relative positions. For example, Lewin's transformational theory deals with sets of objects in multi-dimensional spaces such as his Klang space, where all possible triads are represented as points in a two-dimensional space of *pitch* \times *quality* [3]. Another example of such point objects are the Module denotators used in Rubato Composer [16], which are based on elements of Module spaces, e.g. the Module over the rational numbers \mathbb{Q} . In contrast to such models, the spheres in *HotS* do not consist of positions or directions, but rather trajectories within the space, and could thus be most closely compared to objects in topological spaces. These moving objects exploit the full potential of multitouch devices, with which users typically interact via (pseudo-)continuous finger motions.

Formally, I define a sphere S in the n -dimensional space U as a point $u \in U$ along with a set of n sequences of distances s_i , one for each dimension, i.e.

$$S = (u, \{s_1, \dots, s_n\})$$

with

$$s_i = (\delta_1, \dots, \delta_{p_i}).$$

Each of these sequences s_i describes a motion in the corresponding dimension of U , e.g. the distances of s_3 describe a motion in the third dimension, and the point u describes the sphere's reference position. These motions do not all have to be of the same length, which means that each sequence s_i has its own length $p_i \geq 0$. The simplest configuration of a sphere is one with no motion at all $S = (u, \{(), \dots, ()\})$ with n empty sequences, which is an immobile object in U . For any other possible object, the sequences s_i define its independent motion in the respective i th dimension.

⁶ The app remembers the motions' and conditions' higher-dimensional properties in case the users decide to increase the dimensionality of the space again.

Now how are these objects put in motion in practice? Every sphere starts at its reference point u and then iterates through each sequence s_i independently, but at a synchronous pace. At each step, it adds the current δ_{k_i} to its current position in dimension i . A sphere has thus the potential to oscillate in each dimension with a different periodicity, which can lead to interesting sonic behavior.

Users can add spheres to the space by simply dragging their fingers across the screen (multitouch gestures will result in one sphere added per finger). Depending on the currently selected view configuration VC (see previous section), the motion defined by the finger gesture is recorded and added to a new sphere's dimensions currently associated with the x-axis and y-axis parameters. Then, the users can add motion in other dimensions by switching the perspective by reassigning other dimensions of U to the axis parameters, and drawing new motions from the newly selected perspectives. If they choose to leave some of the dimensions of the motion undefined, they are assigned the empty sequence $()$, which results in a stable position in those dimensions.

In order to ensure maximal usability, *HotS* currently uses a particular kind of spheres: the ones where the elements of each of the motions s_i add up to 0, so that the sphere repeatedly ends up at the starting point in each of the dimensions.⁷ This is taken care of automatically at the time a sphere is defined by the user. After a defining touch gesture as just described, each s_i is completed with an additional element consisting of the inverse of the sum of all previous elements.

A special case to be mentioned here are the spheres in the bounded space $U = [0, 1]^n$. Not every conceivable motion is possible to be executed in such a space. For instance, consider a sphere

$$S = ((0.9, 0.5), \{(0.1, 0.1, -0.2), (0.3, -0.3)\})$$

in $U = [0, 1]^2$. This sphere fulfills the condition described in the previous paragraph, where the sum of the elements of each dimension is 0, and the motion is thus cyclical. However, the sphere will quickly reach the edge of the space and not be able to continue its gesture appropriately. Specifically, it starts at position $(0.9, 0.5)$, then moves to $(1, 0.8)$, where it cannot continue to the hypothetical next position $(1.1, 0.5)$. We solve this problem by ensuring that any motion past the edge of the space leaves the sphere at the edge. In this case, this leads to position $(1, 0.5)$. Our example sphere will now jump to a new position in the next step, $(0.8, 0.8)$, a position from where its cyclical motion will now be possible $((0.9, 0.5), (1, 0.8), (0.8, 0.5), \dots)$. This solution is in line with the edge collision solution presented in the next section and corresponds with the idea of spheres being objects of mainly relative existence, with only the initial position being defined absolutely, which is crucial when working with physical models.

⁷ Note that this does typically not happen at the same time for each dimension, since the s_i do not have the same length.

5. PHYSICAL TRANSFORMATIONS

In the previous section we saw how each sphere can have its inherent motion, which consists of a repetitive multi-dimensional oscillation. The main idea behind *HotS*, however, is a more global type of motion determined by changing physical conditions defined for the space. In the context of mathematical music theory, these physical motions can be considered a generalized form of transformations, which act upon the musical objects. Such transformations are typically expressed as functions on a set of objects. In classical transformational theory, for instance, they consist of groups of operations on sets [3], whereas in newer topos-theoretical approaches they consist of morphisms, again for instance on the category of Modules [4].

Here, our transformations mainly consist of gravity fields, which are either defined in relation to infinite planes, gravitational centers, or between the spheres themselves. Specifically, the physical transformations used in *HotS* are generalized n -dimensional adaptations of the two- or three-dimensional spatial physics commonly used in simulations or games. Currently, all types of transformations available are gravitational. However, users can also define general physical properties of space and spheres, such as collision properties and the viscosity of the material filling the space.

5.1 Gravitational Transformations

HotS currently supports three kinds of gravitational conditions, which can be combined in any way. At the time these conditions are defined using Newtonian gravitational acceleration functions $a(t)$ which assume an equal mass for all spheres. In an iterative process, all current accelerations are summed up for each sphere and added to their current velocity, thus

$$v_{t+1} = v_t + \sum_i a_i(t)$$

where i iterates through all currently active acceleration functions.

Each of the functions can be precisely configured using a linear factor σ which determines a general *gravitational strength* and takes the role of the masses in Newton's formula. The latter two types add a degree of *exponentiality* ϵ , which determines how much stronger spheres are affected by gravity the closer they are to the gravitational object. For Newtonian gravity, we choose $\epsilon = 2$. These and all other determining factors introduced later on can be changed continuously in realtime, which allows a high degree of control over the resulting soundscapes. Currently, this is realized with long exponentially mapped sliders, which ensures both a high precision and large range for each parameter.

5.1.1 Directional Gravity

The first type of gravity assumes an infinite plane generating a constant directional gravity for the entire space. Independently of any sphere's current position, we get the

constant acceleration function

$$a_{dir} = g\sigma$$

where g is a vector determining the directional gravity.

5.1.2 Central Gravity

For this type of gravity we assume a gravitational center $c \in U$. The acceleration function for the current position p_S of a sphere S is then

$$a_{cen}(p_S) = (c - p_S) \frac{\sigma}{d(p_S, c)^\epsilon}$$

where $d(S, C)$ is the Euclidean distance between the gravitational center and the sphere in question. The result is an acceleration vector resulting from the are multiplied with the distance vector between

If several simultaneous centers of gravitation are defined, we calculate the sum of all such accelerations for each sphere, as specified in the velocity equation above.

5.1.3 Cohesive Gravity

The third type of gravity comes closest to Newtonian gravity, being defined pairwise between all present spheres. We get the following formula for a sphere S and its current position p_S :

$$a_{coh}(p_S) = \sum_{S_j \neq S} (p_{S_j} - p_S) \frac{\sigma}{d(p_S, p_{S_j})^\epsilon}$$

5.2 Physical Properties of Space and Spheres

In addition to the gravitational conditions just described, the users can also define other global physical parameters in real time.

5.2.1 Sphere Collisions

One can activate a collision mechanism based on an repulsive force that is activated as soon as two spheres overlap. It consists of an anti-gravity that is stronger, the more the spheres overlap. We can define this repulsive force as follows

$$\rho \frac{d_{min}}{d}$$

where ρ is the repulsion constant and d_{min} the minimum distance between the spheres (typically the sum of their radiuses) and d their actual distance. This results in a smooth spring-like repulsion where the spheres temporarily overlap. Users can adjust ρ in real time.

A second collision mechanism can be activated when working with $U = [0, 1]^n$. It controls how the spheres are repulsed when they reach the edge of the space. This mechanism works either the same as the sphere algorithm just described, or it can be defined to be more immediate, where the velocity is directly inverted in the respective axis where the maximum or minimum was reached. An additional friction constant ϕ can also be chosen, which defines how much of the momentum is lost due to friction.

5.2.2 Viscosity: Controlling Musical Time

Another global parameter that can be defined in real time is the viscosity v of the space. It determines how fast all the spheres move and can thus be analogized to a global tempo control. v is simply multiplied with the velocity vector resulting from all the calculations, which for $v < 1$ leads to a slower pace of the physics, however, not of the spheres' inherent motions.

5.3 Inherent Motion and Physical Transformations

Now what happens with the inherent motion of each sphere while it is also transformed physically in one of the ways specified above? The inherent motions are still iterated through as it is described in Section 4 and at each step of the iteration, the current distances δ_{k_i} are still traveled in each dimension regardless of the velocity resulting from the physics and before the current effect of the physical conditions are calculated. This has the consequence that spheres maintain their inherent motion relatively, but their overall absolute position varies based on the physics.

This enables users to for instance define spheres that are rapidly modulating their phase or frequency in a vibrato-like fashion, but are moving on a wider trajectory and interacting with each other. The spheres' inherent motion can also lead to favorable effects when the energy of that motion affects the way they collide with each other. Oscillating spheres may eject other spheres from their paths much more energetically than ones with no inherent motion.

5.4 Using the Accelerometer

Directional gravity as well as central gravity can also be varied in realtime using the accelerometer of the device. For directional gravity, the more the device is tilted in a direction, the stronger the gravity gets. For central gravity, the user can move the position of the gravitational center by tilting the device.

5.5 Larger Form: Sequences of Physical Conditions

Even just one physical condition can be used in an improvisatory way by varying its parameters in real time. For instance, a central gravity condition can be moved around, made stronger and weaker, etc, which immediately affects the spheres to react. However, *HotS* also allows users to plan the behavior on a larger scale by defining sequences of physical conditions, each of them lasting for a given duration. This sequence can then either be iterated through once or repeatedly, the latter resulting in a *loop* structure. The total duration of this loop can be varied in real time, by changing the individual durations of the contained physical conditions. Of course, users can also add new spheres at any time, even while physical conditions active.

Instead of looping through the sequence, user may also choose to trigger it several times, with varying musical material (a different set of spheres each time). For this, the app allows users to make the spheres return to their initial position while resetting the sequence of physical conditions to its beginning, before triggering it again.

At a later stage of implementation, the sequence may be replaced by a graph with parallel and alternative edges which can then be traveled in real time, as I implemented it in my earlier project *BigBang* [15].

6. CONCLUSION

This paper gave a brief overview of the concepts and functionality of the current state of *Harmony of the Spheres*. Even at this stage, the sonic capabilities of the app are vast, especially when used in combination with external sound generators. It may act as a counterpoint to commonly used skeuomorphic controllers such as *TouchOSC*, where the conceptual parametric dimensions are usually uncorrelated.

Apart from the potential extensions mentioned in the text, there are several other ones that I plan to work on in the future. In addition to the dimensions of the space, users will soon also be able to choose to map some of the physical quantities of the spheres, such as velocity, direction of motion, etc, to visual and auditive dimensions, just as it was done in [13] or [14]. With the current physical model, described in Section 5, useful quantities would for instance be the absolute value of a sphere's current velocity, which possibly most closely corresponds to the ancient notion of the harmony of the spheres. Other values that can be mapped are the current direction vector, or the strength of collisions.

Another extension especially well-suited for multi-touch devices are topological transformations of the space itself, or the definition of transformative force fields more complex than gravitational fields, which could be considered extensions of the common multitouch gestures.

Finally, the support of external control devices, such as MIDI controllers or the Leap Motion could further extend the degree of interactivity experienced by the users.

7. REFERENCES

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